

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS PLAN

“Pilot Study to estimate the potential efficacy and safety of using Adjunctive Ibuprofen for the Treatment of pre-XDR and XDR Tuberculosis”.

Code: NSAIDS-XDR-TB

Sample size was decided based on feasibility, gains in the precision about the mean and variance, and regulatory considerations according to literature on pilot studies (1,2). Results of ibuprofen-treated group will be compared to those obtained in the group of patients treated with SoC alone, which will be considered controls. Patients offered to enrol the study and who preferred not to will might also be considered as controls.

This is a pilot, thus to see the magnitude and direction of possible responses, and not powered to show smaller differences. We plan to use the data generated to design a larger trial. All hypothesis tests in this pilot will be prespecified as exploratory.

Both primary and secondary analyses followed an intention-to-treat (ITT) approach including all randomized participants with available data.

Descriptive statistics for patient demographic data, clinical and radiographic parameters, comorbidities, co-infection, full laboratory data including blood indices, blood chemistries, as well as all microbiological data will be performed. Continuous variables will be reported as medians and interquartile ranges (IQR) and compared with the Mann–Whitney U test; categorical data presented as counts and percentages. Absolute risk differences with 95% CIs will be calculated using the Newcombe method. For radiological outcomes ratios at month 3 (M3/BL) and month 6 (M6/BL) will be calculated, considering ratios <1 as favourable. Health-related quality-of-life good responders will be defined as normal range values (SGRQ ≤ 7 and K10 <20) at both months 2 and 6. Immune response changes will be expressed as ratios to baseline and compared with the Mann–Whitney U test.

REFERENCES

1. Julious SA. Sample size of 12 per group rule of thumb for a pilot study. *Pharmaceutical Statistics* 2005; 4: 287–91.
2. Whitehead AL, Julious SA, Cooper CL, Campbell MJ. Estimating the sample size for a pilot randomised trial to minimise the overall trial sample size for the external pilot and main trial for a continuous outcome variable. *Statistical Methods in Medical Research* 2016; 25. DOI:10.1177/0962280215588241.